

Product Wavefunction $W_0(x)W_1(x)$ (W_0 =ground state) Approach to the 3D Hypergeometric Equation

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In a previous note, we argued one may write the bound state wavefunction as $W(x)=W_0(x)W_1(x)$, where $W_0(x)$ is the bound ground state wavefunction. This was then applied to the one dimensional case, yielding a coupled equation for $W_1(x)$:

$$-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1 - 1/m \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{W_0}{W_0} \right) \left(\frac{d}{dx} W_1 \right) = (E-E_0) W_1(x) \quad ((1))$$

A transformation may bring ((3)) into the hypergeometric form (1):

$$p(x) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + q(x) \frac{d}{dx} W + \text{constant} W = 0 \quad ((2))$$

with $p(x)$ at most quadratic in x and q linear. Then, a Rodrigues polynomial solution exists and:

$$\text{Constant} = -(E-E_0) = -n/2 \left(\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} p (n-1) + 2 \frac{d}{dx} q \right) \quad ((3))$$

In a 3D problem with a potential depending on r alone, one may also obtain a “one dimensional” looking Schrodinger equation with an additional term $-l(l+1)/(r^*r)$ (l =the angular momentum eigenvalue). As a result, one may try to apply the approach of ((1)) to this radial equation and force the coefficient of $d/dr W_1$ to be $ar+b$ (or $ay+b$ after a transformation $y=f(r)$). When carrying out the analysis, however, one may find that the imposed $ay+b$ leads to $l=0$, i.e. eliminates the $l(l+1)/(r^*r)$ term. Then, one has a hypergeometric solution, but this does not correspond, it seems, to the original problem, which has an l present. One may try to argue that the original problem with l not zero in general, will have a set of solutions for which l is 0 and that these should obey a DE with the term $l(l+1)/(r^*r)$ removed. That may be the case, but solving an $l=0$ DE does not lead to the same energy levels of the original problem which holds for all l , including $l=0$. We investigate this in this note.

First, we consider the 3D harmonic oscillator with a potential of $.5k r^*r$ and transform it using $W=r^{(l+1)} v_1$. Next, a second transformation $s^*s=y$ is used to bring the equation into hypergeometric form for all l values. This then yields correct energy levels. Next, we consider solving the DE with $l=0$. This is not the original DE and the solutions do not yield the correct energy levels (although the correct levels are included as a subset). Using $W=r^{(l+1)} v_1$ and the coupled equation ((1)) is then investigated.

Finally, we consider a potential of:

$$V(r) = [A \exp(-2qr) + B + C \exp(2qr)] / [\exp(2qr) (1-\exp(-2qr))^2] \quad ((4))$$

with energy levels given by the Nikiforov-Uvarov method given as ((5))

$$Enl = C - 2q^*q/m \{ [n(n+1) + l(l+1) + .5(1 + (mB+2mC)/(q^*q) + \sqrt{(1+21)^2 + 2m/(q^*q)(C+B-A)}) (n+.5)] / [(1+2n + \sqrt{(1+21)^2 + 2m/(q^*q)(C+B-A)})] \}$$

We then consider the problem with a DE with $l=0$. This DE, however, is the one dimensional problem, not the 3D one. We show it leads to very different energy level results, even though it should have the appearance of the 3D equation for $l=0$ only results. This shows that one cannot simply set $l=0$ in a 3D equation and obtain information about the $l=0$ only energy levels. It is possible that a subset of the solutions of the DE with $l=0$ apply, but one does not know which subset, hence the energy levels of the DE with l set to 0 may not be very meaningful.

The Three Dimensional Harmonic Oscillator

Here the potential $.5 m \omega^2 r^2$ is used leading to a radial Schrodinger equation of (3):

$$d/dy d/dy v - 2y d/dy v + [2c - 1 - l(l+1)/(y^*y)] v = 0 \text{ with } c=E/w \text{ and } y=\sqrt{mw} r. \text{ ((6))}$$

Consider a solution of: $v = v_1 * y^{l+1}$. Then ((6)) becomes:

$$d/dy d/dy v_1 - 2y d/dy v_1 + 2(l+1)/y d/dy v_1 + [2c-1- 2(l+1)] v_1 = 0 \text{ ((7))}$$

Next, one makes the transformation: $s=y^*y$ or $d/dy v_1 = (d/ds v_1) 2y$ and $d/dy d/dy v_1 = (d/ds d/ds v_1) 4y^*y + 4y (d/ds v_1)$

Then ((7)) becomes:

$$4s d/ds d/ds v_1 + (d/ds v_1)[2 - 4s + 4(l+1)] + [2c-1- 2(l+1)] v_1 = 0 \text{ ((8))}$$

This is of the form of a hypergeometric equation with $p(s)=4s$ and $q(s)= [2 - 4s + 4(l+1)]$. Thus, ((5)) yields:

$$[2c-1- 2(l+1)] = 2n \text{ or } E = (w) [l + 3/2 + 2n] \text{ ((9))}$$

This is the energy equation for the oscillator. "n" in ((9)) is usually written as k and is 0,1,2..

Let us now consider the method of ((1)). Is it possible to obtain any information about energy levels? We write $v = v_0 v_b$ where v_0 is the ground state solution and use this in ((6)) to obtain:

$$d/dy d/dy v_b + 2 (d/dy v_b) (d/dy v_a / v_a) - 2y d/dy v_b + [2(E-E_0)/w] v = 0 \text{ ((10))}$$

One solution leading to a hypergeometric equation is:

$$2d/dy v_a/v_a - 2 y = ay+b \text{ ((11)) (It must be linear.) Let } g(y) = d/dy v_a / v_a$$

Then: $.5(a+2)y + .5b = g$ ((12)) let $a_1 = a+2$

We know: $d/dy g + g^*g = d/dy d/dy v_a$ so ((6)) becomes:

$$d/dy g + g^*g - 2y g + [2E_0/w - 1 - l(l+1)/(y^*y)] = 0 \quad ((13))$$

We can insert ((12)) into ((13)), multiply by y^*y and compare powers of y .

[coefficient of constant power] $l(l+1)=0$ so $l=0$ This is already problematic because all l values should be allowed.

$$[\text{coefficient of } y^4] \quad \frac{1}{4} a_1^*a_1 - a_1 = 0 \text{ or } a_1 = 4 \text{ or } a = 2$$

$$[\text{coefficient of } y^3] \quad \frac{1}{4} a_1^*b - b = 0$$

[coefficient of y^*y] $(2E_0/w - 1) + .5a_1 = 0$ This does not lead to the correct ground state for a 3D oscillator.

The point is that $a=2$ so $2(E-E_0)/w = n a = 2n$ which is not correct.

Looking at ((10)), with l set to 0, as a hypergeometric solution shows that

$$2(E-E_0)/w = -n a \quad ((14))$$

This is also incorrect.

Thus, it is dangerous to set $l=0$ in a 3D equation and solve it, thinking it will yield information about the energy levels of the set of $l=0$ only solutions. In the case above, one may note that the energy levels $E = w(2n+1+3/2)$ are contained in the solutions, but there are other solutions as well. In another example, we will see that the energy levels for the 3D equation with l set to 0 can be completely different from those solved for the general 3D problem.

Next, let us consider the method of ((1)) applied to ((7)) i.e.

$$d/dy d/dy v_1 + -2y d/dy v_1 + 2(l+1)/y d/dy v_1 + [2c-1- 2(l+1)] v_1 = 0 \quad ((7))$$

Set $v_1 = v_0 v_2$ where v_0 is a ground state solution of ((7)). Then:

$$d/dy d/dy v_2 + 2(d/dy v_2) g - 2y d/dy v_2 + 2(E-E_0)/w v_2 = 0 \quad ((8))$$

Where $g = d/dy \ v_0 / v_0$. Forcing ((8)) to be a hypergeometric equation leads to one possible condition: $2g - 2y = ay + b$ or $g = .5(a_1y + b)$ where $a_1 = a + 2$. Then ((7)) becomes:

$$d/dy (g) + g^*g - 2y g + 2(l+1)/y g + [2E_0/w - 1 - 2(l+1)] = 0 \quad \text{or}$$

This still leads to $l=0$ for a solution, so it cannot be used. One needs a transformation $s^*s=y$ in ((7)) which still allows for a hypergeometric form, but which will add a y to cancel that of $2(l+1)/y g$. Thus, it seems one may use the method of ((1)) for the 3D radial equation, provided the hypergeometric solution apply to all l values and not $l=0$ only. An equation with $l=0$ only does not seem to yield the energy levels of even the $l=0$ only solutions.

Method of ((1)) and a Potential of ((4))

Let us first consider the transformation $y = \exp(-2qr)$ for the potential given by ((4)). Then the Schrodinger equation is (1):

$$d/dr \ d/dr \ R + 2m \{ E - [A \exp(-2qr) + B + C \exp(2qr)] / [\exp(2qr) (1 - \exp(-2qr)^2) - [2l(l+1) q^*q \exp(-2qr)] / [m(1 - \exp(-2qr))] \} R = 0 \quad ((15))$$

One may see that the usual $2l(l+1)/(r^*r)$ term has been replaced with an approximation using $\exp(-2qr)$. See (1) for details.

We consider the $l=0$ case, but as one can see from ((15)), this is now the one dimensional problem and not the 3D radial one. The 1D DE even has different properties in terms of the interchange of parameters.

For $l=0$, $d/dr \ d/dr \ R = 4q^*q y^*y \ d/dy \ d/dy + 4q^*q y \ d/dy$ and:

$$V(y) = [Ay^*y + By + C] / [(1-y)^2] \quad ((15))$$

For $l=0$ and $y = \exp(2qr)$ $d/dr \ d/dr \ R = 4q^*q y^*y \ d/dy \ d/dy + 4q^*q y \ d/dy$ and:

$$V(y) = [A + By + Cy^*y] / [(1-y)^2] \quad ((16))$$

Thus, for $l=0$, the Schrodinger equation using $y = \exp(-2qr)$ will be the same as that with $y = \exp(2qr)$ and C and A exchanged. Both equations may be solved using the Nikiforov-Uvarov method of (1) and should yield ((5)) for $y = \exp(-2qr)$ and ((5)) with C and A interchanged for $y = \exp(2qr)$. In both cases, however, one has the same physical problem, so the energy levels should be the same. Thus, ((5)) should be invariant under an interchange of C and A if $l=0$, but it is not. This shows the one dimensional problem is not the same as the 3D radial situation with $l=0$. In general, with l not 0, interchanging A and C changes ((15)) in a much more radical way because of the $2l(l+1)$ term.

Let us examine the method of ((4)) with $l=0$ (i.e. a one dimensional problem) and $B=0$ and $y=\exp(-2qr)$. The Schrodinger equation is:

$$4q^*q y^*y \frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} R + 4q^*q y \frac{d}{dy} R + [2mE - 2mAy^*/(1-y)^2 - 2mC/(1-y)^2] R = 0 \quad ((17))$$

Let $R=R_0 v_1$ where R_0 is the ground state solution for $l=0, B=0$. Then:

$$4q^*q y^*y \left[\frac{d}{dy} \frac{d}{dy} v_1 + 2g \frac{d}{dy} v_1 \right] + 4q^*q y \frac{d}{dy} v_1 = -2m(E-E_0) v_1 \text{ where } g = \frac{d}{dy} R_0 / R_0. \quad ((18))$$

For a hypergeometric equation, we impose:

$$8q^*q y^*y g + 4q^*q y = ay+b \text{ or } g = (a_1y+b) / (8q^*q y^*y) \text{ where } a_1 = a - 4q^*q \quad ((19))$$

Substituting ((19)) into ((18)) yields:

$$-a_1y^*y - by + (1/(16q^*q)) [a_1^*a_1 y^*y + b^*b + 2a_1b y] + .5a_1 y^*y + .5(a_1y^*y+by) + 2mmE_0y^*y - 2mAy^4 / (1-y)^2 - 2mCy^*/(1-y)^2 = 0 \quad ((20))$$

Multiplying by $(1-y)^2$ and equating powers of y yields:

$$[\text{coefficient of } y] -b-b^*b/(8q^*q) + a_1^*b/(8q^*q) + .5b = 0 \quad \text{This gives } b(a_1, q)$$

$$[\text{coefficient of } y^*y] -2mC + 2mE_0 -a_1 + 2b + a_1^*a_1/(16q^*q) + b^*b/(16q^*q) - a_1^*b/(4q^*q) + a_1/2 + .5a_1 -b = 0$$

$$[\text{coefficient of } y^3] -4E_0m -a_1 + .5b -a_1 -a_1^*a_1/(8q^*q) + a_1^*b/(8q^*q) -b + 2a_1 = -$$

$$[\text{coefficient of } y^4] 2mE_0 - 2mA + .5a_1 + .5a_1 + a_1^*a_1/(16q^*q) -a_1 = 0$$

One may subtract the [coefficient of y^*y] and [coefficient of y^4] and use $b(a_1, q)$ to obtain an equation for $a_1(q)$. One may note that the new equation contains A and C on the same footing, so they may be interchanged without changing anything. This is in keeping the two transformations $y=\exp(-2qr)$ and $y=\exp(2qr)$ yielding the same energy levels.

At this point, we wish to solve the above problem for $C=0$ and $A=q^*q/(2m^*m)$. We find:

$$b = a - 8q^*q$$

The combination of the [coefficient of y^*y] and [coefficient of y^4] gives a quadratic for a (where $a_1 = a - 4q^*q$).

$5/(16q^*q) a^*a -2a + [-q^*q/m + q^*q] = 0$ This can be solved for $a(q)$.

Finally: $2mE_0 -q^*q/m + a^1a^1/(16q^*q) = 0$ This yields E_0 (for $l=0, B=C=0, A=q^*q/(2m^*m)$) as a function of q .

It seems that one may obtain a hypergeometric form for the W_0, v_1 coupled equation (for $l=0, B=C=0, A=q^*q/(2m^*m)$). This means here should be energy levels given by:

$$l=0 \quad -2m (E-E_0) = -n/2 (8q^*q (n-1) + a) \quad \text{where } a \text{ is the solution of the quadratic. } ((21))$$

This result, however, applies to the 1D case and not the 3D one, even the set of $l=0$ solutions.

The 1D ground state wavefunction may also be found as:

$$d/dy \ln(W_0) = (a_1y+b) / (8q^*q y^*y) \quad \text{or } \ln(W_0) = \text{Integral } (a_1y+b)/(8q^*q y^*y) dy \quad \text{or}$$

$W_0 = \exp[-a_1/(8q^*q) \ln(y) - 1/ (8q^*q^*y)]$. Thus, the method of ((4)) is useful for the 1D problem, but not for the 3D one, unless an appropriate transformation may be found which will allow the approach to apply to all l values and not only the $l=0$ case.

In other words, the 3D problem solutions, even for $l=0$, are not the same as the 1D energy levels, even though ((15)), with $l=0$, is the 1D equation. This seems to indicate that when solving a 3D radial problem, one cannot use the method of ((1)) unless it applies to all l values. If, during the analysis, one is forced to set $l=0$ in order to have a hypergeometric form, then the method is not applicable to the 3D problem, it seems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems one may apply the method of ((1)) (the product wavefunction method) to a radial equation containing $l(l+1)$ and try to force ((1)) to be of a hypergeometric form. If the analysis, however, shows this can only occur for $l=0$, the method is not suitable and one must consider transformations which allows for all l to be included (as shown for the 3D oscillator). In a case considered, setting $l=0$ in a 3D radial DE converts it into the 1D problem. The 1D problem may be easily solved using the method of ((1)), the energy levels do not correspond to the $l=0$ only ones of the 3D radial DE, even though the equations for the 1D problem and the $l=0$ 3D problem appear the same.

References

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